

Principles of Accounting Unit 16

Common Size Ratio Analysis: Beyond the Numbers Case Study

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CASE OUTLINE (2025 EDITION)

Financial ratio analysis is an important skill for business leaders. It can help to benchmark performance within an industry or compare companies across industries.

You should compare five real companies in different industries using the following data:

- Common size balance sheet (Case Exhibit 1)
- Common size income statement (Case Exhibit 2)
- Selected financial ratios (Case Exhibit 3).

Data has been rounded.

A key to the ratio calculations is included in Case Exhibit 4.

All 5 companies are listed in the UK. Their financial information is typical of their sector. Using the case exhibits, you are asked to identify the industry of companies A to E, from the following:

- Supermarket chain
- Online-only retailer
- Housebuilder
- Airline
- Delivery company (food)

HINT: Review the data carefully for the key characteristics of each industry e.g. structure of the statement of financial position, income statement profile.

SKILLS DEVELOPED

Completing this case develops the following skills:

Knowledge and understanding – understanding of the operational context of different companies and the impact on their financial statements and ratios.

Application skills – application of ratio analysis to real data.

Communication skills – explaining the process used to match the data with the industry.

Exhibit 1

Case Exhibit 1	A	B	C	D	E
Revenues	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Cost of sales	(60%)		(93%)	(88%)	(63%)
Gross profit	40%	100%	7%	12%	37%
Operating expenses	(51%)	(94%)	(4%)	(8%)	(38%)
Operating profit	(11%)	6%	3%	4%	(1%)
Non-operating items					
Finance income		2%		1%	1%
Finance costs	(2%)	(1%)	(1%)	(1%)	0
Profit before tax	(13%)	7%	2%	4%	1%
Income tax expense	1%	(2%)	(1%)	(1%)	(1%)
Profit for the year	(12%)	5%	1%	3%	0%

Exhibit 2

Case Exhibit 2	A	B	C	D	E
Goodwill	2%	4%	3%	11%	
Other intangible assets	21%	4%		2%	7%
Property, plant and equipment	12%	50%	38%	1%	3%
Right of use assets (leases)	11%		18%	1%	5%
Deferred tax assets	3%				
Other		2%	6%	7%	1%
Total non-current assets	50%	59%	66%	16%	16%
Current assets					
Inventories	23%		8%	67%	1%
Trade receivables	2%	1%	1%	1%	6%
Other receivables		3%			
Cash and cash equivalents	17%	12%	11%	14%	49%
Other investments		19%			22%
Other financial assets					
Other	1%	5%	4%	3%	5%
Total current assets	43%	41%	24%	84%	84%
Assets held for sale	7%		10%		
Total assets	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Exhibit 2 continued.

Case Exhibit 2	A	B	C	D	E
Current liabilities					
Trade payables	5%	3%	16%		4%
Other payables	26%	37%	18%	18%	45%
Held for sale			12%		
Total current liabilities	31%	40%	46%	18%	49%
Non-current liabilities					
Borrowings and other financial liabilities	30%	15%	20%	3%	
Other	16%	18%	7%	10%	5%
Total non-current liabilities	46%	33%	27%	13%	5%
Total liabilities	77%	73%	73%	31%	54%
Equity					
Called up share capital	0%	2%	3%	1%	1%
Share premium	14%	20%	6%	3%	
Other reserves etc	3%	(1%)		14%	148%
Retained earnings	6%	6%	18%	50%	(103%)
Total equity	23%	27%	27%	69%	46%
Liabilities plus equity	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Exhibit 3

Case Exhibit 3	A	B	C	D	E
Liquidity					
Cash ratio	0.17	0.12	0.11	0.14	0.49
Acid test ratio	0.88	1.02	0.35	0.90	1.68
Current ratio	1.61	1.02	0.52	4.55	1.71
Efficiency					
Accounts receivable days	6.71	5.29	1.76	6.32	10.78
Inventory turnover	3.35		15.72	0.69	98.12
Inventory days	108.94		23.22	526.56	3.72
Asset turnover	1.28	0.84	1.33	0.53	2.19
Accounts payable days	22.63		46.57		9.82
Working capital Cycle (days)	93.01		(21.59)	532.89	4.68
Financial leverage					
Debt to total assets	30%	15%	20%	3%	0%
Debt to equity	1.32	0.57	0.74	0.04	
Profitability					
Gross margin (%)	40%	100%	7%	12%	37%
Operating margin (%)	(11.4%)	6.3%	2.8%	4.2%	(0.6%)
Interest cover (x)	(5.59)	4.46	2.58	3.25	(3.18)

Exhibit 4 – Key to ratio calculations

Ratio	Calculation
Liquidity	
Cash ratio	Cash/Total assets
Acid test ratio	(Current Assets-Inventory)/Current Liabilities
Current ratio	Current Assets/Current Liabilities
Efficiency	
Accounts receivables days	(Accounts receivable/Revenues)*365
Inventory turnover	Inventory/Revenue
Inventory days	(Inventory/Cost of Sales)*365
Asset turnover	Revenue/ Total Assets
Accounts payable days	(Accounts Payable/Cost of Sales)*365
Working capital cycle	AR + Inventory days – AP days
Financial leverage ratios	
Debt to total assets	Long-term borrowings/total assets
Debt to equity	Long-term borrowings/total equity
Profitability ratios	
Gross margin %	Gross profit/revenue
Operating margin	Operating profit/revenue
Interest cover	Finance costs/operating profit

References

Lev, B., (2018). The deteriorating usefulness of financial report information and how to reverse it, *Accounting and Business Research*, 48(5), 465-493. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00014788.2018.1470138>

Coull, M. & Douglas, S. (2024). How can reported data be used? Unit 16 in Smith, S., Murphy, R. & Rose, J., *Principles of Accounting*. Available at: www.accounting-streams.org